

Who needs genetic diversity when you have a flexible genome?

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Introduction:

- Many invasive species have low or no genetic variation¹
- E.g. highly invasive fountain grass has no genetic variation^{2,3}, but invades diverse environments
- Phenotypic variation in fountain grass is possibly due to epigenetic mechanisms such as DNA methylation that change how DNA is expressed without changing the DNA sequence itself

Figure 1:

Methylation (CH₂-group shown as Me) generally acts as an "off" switch for gene expression when present and an "on" switch when absent

Results:

- **No DNA variation** with ISSR analysis

Table 1: Proportion of methylation across all loci and position of methyl group associated with cytosine

	North Cape (NC)	West Cape (WC)	Possible implication
Unmethylated	0.1839	0.2844	none
Hemi-methylated	0.1458	0.09052	Fixed mark during replication
Internal cytosine methylated	0.5259	0.43621	Gene regulation⁴
Full methylation or absence of target	0.1444	0.18879	none

- 1st report of epigenetic population structure in a natural population
- Multivariate analysis shows clear clustering of populations according to origin (environment)
- Epigenetic responses to environmental differences must facilitate phenotypic plasticity
- Majority of methylation differences due to methylation of inner cytosine which have been implied in gene regulation⁴

Experimental design:

Figure 2: Samples were collected in Garies, Northern Cape (NC), and Gordons Bay in the Western Cape (WC)

Figure 3: MS-AFLP analysis follows same procedure as AFLPs but use methylation sensitive enzymes which results in different profiles if methylation (CH₂) is present or absent

Figure 4: Principle coordinate analysis (PCoA) which shows percentage of variance explained by both axes. Points represent individual plants (Red = Northern Cape, Blue= Western Cape)

References:

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